
NAAC RECOGNIZED BEST PRACTICES IN ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

The academic institution provides education and that education is embedded in library. As, we all know library is the heart of every academic institution, the library is playing role of heart as a purifier, giving pure blood to body, like that library strains good, original, essential information to readers. An Academic library has to function as a central gateway for library users to access, locate, transform and utilize information resources. In the age of Information Explosion, the era of ICT(Information Communication Technology) academic libraries are undergoing transformation although, library professional gives best services to academic library users and they need to redefine their role. In the present electronic environment, librarians required to work independently or as a team to deliver service oriented and user applications, instructions, programmes, projects and services. Librarians are using their innovative ideas to attract the library users, in order to cope up with modern technologies and attract more number of library users professionals must adopt best practices. My paper is focus on all types of best practices which serves the objectives and motives of academic purpose of libraries and the practices which are best for NAAC purpose.

Key Words: Library, ICT, Professional, Ideas, Best Practice.

Introduction:

Every Academic Institution has a library and a library is the mirror of that institution. It shows or reflects the objectives and current status of particular academy. It indicates the futuristic plans as well as the history which focuses on the reliability of individual institutions. They mark some status about the institution and rankings. Not only the library serve the needs of users but taking consideration of the importance of library now a days they are recommended as a Knowledge Resource Centers and the librarians are the Director of Knowledge Resource Centers. In the process of Institutional

Accreditation, libraries have a crucial role, the services of the libraries have been expanding as they contribute significantly to the learning process, particularly the e-learning process.

Quality improvement without Best Practices and Accreditation cannot be possible. Best practices are identified by examining empirical evidence of success.

It is institutional accreditation that the NAAC does the assessment of a library, Its a vital sub unit and a key step that integrates itself with the overall evaluation. As well the library evaluation is an essential component in the accreditation process where the collection, services and

their outreaching capacity are monitored. In the recent past significant developments have been reported in the library and information services and the libraries are shouldering newer responsibilities. In higher education libraries largely supported learning, teaching and research process in institutions.

The Quality enhancement is essential for the institutions and country. Mostly the institutions set some goals to achieve the objectives and mission. **1.**

Though, the best practices are different from other institutions and may these best practices makes every institution different. It is strength of the particular institutions and depends on the management, stake holders like student, employee hierarchy. So, Library management is important thing in any kind of library. **2.**

Definition of Best Practices:

A 'Best Practice' in simple term is known as the practice which paves the way for enhancing the existing functions and helping in effective implementation or use of the process.

ODLIS (Online Dictionary of Library and Information Science) describes best practices as follows: "In the application of theory to real life situation, procedures that when properly, applied consistently yield superior results and are there of used as reference points in evaluation of the effectiveness of alternative methods of accomplishing the same task, best practices are identified by examining empirical evidence of success."

According to **Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary**:

"Best practices as quality of high standard, excellence, highly improved, outstanding, par excellence service. It means way of doing something that is

usual or expected way in a particular organization or situation, guidelines for good practices."

This process of developing best practices, action is important. In an Academic library, student and teachers are the customers who are part of academic community.

Radhakrishnan (1948) and Kothari (1964) commission reports have already recognized the role of libraries in higher education. They had recommended the need of a first class library for the college and universities.

Need for the Best Practices:

Libraries are in the service business. The most important product is 'Library Service'. Service is a pervasive ethic of the profession of librarianship. Colleges libraries need to have facilitated that promote effective and interactive access and use of information resource for all users. The libraries need to offer safe, comfortable, well lighted, clean space with adequate and appropriate seating arrangement to ensure effective use of library resources including digital resources as well college libraries are required to consider study space needs. The libraries need seating space with special attention being paid to reserve collection, so, well framed rules and guidelines with regard to hours of access, circulation policies and other regulations to offer better services should be needed. **3**

The Information Communication Technology (ICT) revolution in the last decade has had a drastic and far reaching impact on all aspects of professional endeavour including library services and its work. The users now expect quick service. Performance of the library is measured in terms of effectiveness and efficiency of its service.

Role of libraries in the era of information explosion in 21st century is very important. Library tries to provide maximum service provide to students, staff and external clientele in minimum cost. College form the integral part of higher education and libraries in colleges are the primary source for learning process the library is a connecting link between teaching and learning as well as place which supplements the information. **4**

The role of library among higher education is indisputable. The best practices adopted should bridge the gap between library and users for maximum utilization of the resources. Academic libraries are undergoing transformation. This is the age of technology, Library professionals gives best services to academic library users. Professionals need to redefine their role. The library has to function as a central gateway for library users to access, locate, transform and utilize information resources in a variety of printed and electronic formats via applications, databases, networks, platforms and systems. In this environment academic libraries are required to work independently or as a term to deliver service oriented and user applications, instructions, programmes, projects and services. Library has to provide users with dynamic equipment, facilities, resources and services to support their learning activities which cover assignments, presentations, research papers, also, the libraries shall provide best supporting and training facilities and instructors for designing, developing, integrating and implementing of various teaching courses. **5**

Need of New Technologies in Academic Libraries:

1. To Improve Services of Academic Libraries.
2. To Fulfill information needs of users
3. To fulfill strategic goals of organization
4. Achieve improvement in the performance
5. To accept the challenges posed by technology.

Best Practices Developed and Adopted in Academic Library:

In most of the academic libraries have adopted ICT based services. Technological revolution affected every factor in the society and its major impact is seen on libraries and its services. The library is the chief and significant requirement for any educational institution. In earlier times academic libraries were providing services only the users who used to visit the library as well the ways to build a library collection and offer services to end users vary from the recent to past practices, so academic libraries need to identify and adopt good and best practices and benchmarks. **6**

The prime function of any library is to provide efficient services to its users. The library services are vital forces to achieve academic standards. It is a place where the user searches information of their interest, quality, efficiency, reliability and competitiveness are the watchwords for the library professionals for their survival and growth. Today the libraries are knowledge resource center. It depends on not only the good collection but the good and co- operative staff and the services by providing through the libraries. Dr. S. R. Rangnathan, father of library science suggested the aim of a service through the acronyms 'SPEED' means.

S- Specific Subject, P- Pin Pointed, E- Exhaustive, E- Expeditions, D- Dissemination of Information.

The academic libraries need to identify and adopt good and best practices and benchmarks which will ultimately enhance the value based services of the libraries in an academic environment (NAAC 03). The **Best Practice** in simply means the practice which paves the way for enhancing the existing functions and helps in effective implementation or use of the process. Best practice as a means for continuous learning through sustainable innovation. NAAC strives for quality and excellence in higher education and advocates for enhancing the role of library and information services in improving academic environment. **6**

For College libraries NAAC has developed the following set of best practices. Effective best practices that student used and satisfied are :-

1. Computerization of library with standard digital software.
2. Displaying newspaper clippings on the notice board periodically.
3. Career/ Employment information services.
4. Internet facilities to different user groups.
5. Displaying new arrivals and circulating a list of those to academic departments.
6. Conducting book exhibitions on different occasions.
7. Organizing Book Talks.
8. Instituting Annual Best User Award for students.
9. Organizing competitions annually. **7**

NAAC recognized **Best Practices** in following corners of any institutions.

1. Management and Administration of Library
2. Collection and Services

3. Extent of user services
4. Use of Technology.

For assessing the quality of higher education in the country, NAAC providing the useful guidelines to improve the overall quality of Library and information center and services offered by these centers.

The **Best Practices** are:

1. Inclusion of sufficient information about the library in the college prospectus.
2. Compiling students – teachers' attendance statistics and locating the same on the notice board.
3. Information Literacy programs.
4. Suggestion box and timely response.
5. Conducting use surveys periodically.
6. Library services to external users
7. Book bank facility
8. Information about competitive exams

Colleges form the integral part of higher education and libraries in colleges are the primary source for learning process. The library is a connecting link between teaching and learning as well as place which supplements the information. **8**

The library has a key role in supporting the academic activities of the institutions by establishing, maintaining and promoting library and information services, qualitative and quantitative. The library offers a wide range of services from reference to electronic information services. In this 21st century, ICT plays a important role in library, number of books, journals are available in the form of CD's, DVD's, ,E-books, E-Journals, E-resources and online databases. Accreditation criteria need to introduce IT in libraries as well colleges are highly involved in research activity, so l they need recent information.

Library user, Library resources and Human resource are important components of library. Use of N-List programs, database, library use for society program, library short term courses, training to use

E- resources, smart identity card, display of various charts, keeping the library premises neat and clean are some of the best library practices. All these activities will help for improving quality of library services. As well Use of ICT in library will help for improving quality of library services. These practices will help to inculcate good environment among the user community.

Library has to adopt the new changes, educate the reader community and lead for the nation building.

There are some **General Best Practices**:

1. Regular library advisory committee meeting
2. Binding of Books and Periodical volumes
3. Library orientation for fresh students
4. Reading room and night study room
5. Suggestion box
6. College library website and information of library on College website
7. Use of CCTV for security surveillance
8. Intercom facility for easy communication among various departments
9. Pasting of barcode, spine label and stamping in a definite place on the books
10. Question sets of previous examinations
11. Events and activity calendar of library.
12. Use of pesticides for keeping away book worm and damage of books **9**.

Suggestions for Making Maximum Utilization of library:

1. Make a library PPT which contains last 5 yrs. Data of library, including with Footfall of users, User statistics, Books, Journals, Newspapers, Magazines procured.
2. Collection of previous years
3. Extra library card issue to topper students.
4. News paper clippings should arrange year wise

5. Suggestion box or suggestion register should be maintained in the library for valuable suggestions.
6. ICT enabled services, Digital library services
7. Resource Development-management
8. Notice board should be updated and library rules, do and don'ts, Current notices stick on notice board.
9. Print Journals scanned contents should be sent via e-mail to regarding faculty members, if they required full article then visit in the library.
10. Student – Faculty entry register should maintain for 5 years.
11. E-Resources usage statistics of users.
12. Indoor plants should be in the library for green environment
13. Stock verification records file.
14. New arrivals are displayed in separate section
15. Workshop/ Seminars / Conference / Book exhibition should arranged every year by our library
16. Celebration of / Organise Birth anniversary of Dr. S.R. Ranganathan and special eminent personalities in India to pay tribute.
17. Best User Award to users
18. Special care of Divyanga's to search library material and ramp for them
19. Organizing Competitions annually for emphasizing library importance.
20. Give reply positively to all questions of clientele **10**.

Professional Skills for College Librarians:

Academic Libraries are facing many challenges posed by contemporary environment. All this is result of ICT and digital revolution. The library is changing its traditional concept rapidly, now librarians are facing technological pressure

due to new technologies, software, electronic security systems, virtual libraries, online libraries implemented all over the World. Therefore, librarians are expected to cope up with all these changing environment. In earlier times, academic libraries were providing services only the users who used to visit the library as well the ways to build a library collection and offer services to end users vary from recent to past practices, so academic libraries are need to identify and adopt good and best practices and benchmarks.

Librarians are using their innovative ideas to attract the library users and to convert 'non users to users', In order to cope with modern technologies and attract more number of library users, librarians should adopt **Library Extension Services**: 1. External Membership Facility – To provide service to the society, this facility is useful for general users ,they can be given some nominal fees. 2. Inter Library Loan 3. Document Delivery Service 4. Earn and Learn Scheme 5. Reprography 6. Provision for separate Desk for discussion 7. Career Notification 8. Feedback Register 9. Journal Alert 10. Current Awareness Service specifically for Research Students and Staff 11. Departmental library 12. Library Help Desk for guide the users about library resources 13. Library Security through CCTV camera, 3 M Technology at the entry gate, 14. Seperate Property Counter

Other Services:

1. Use of Signage for easy access. 2. Regular cleanliness of library premises and stacking cupboards 3. Conducting User surveys periodically 11.

Web Based Services:

The Libraries can provide various web based services through its library website and updated with services such as Virtual Tour, Virtual Reference Desk, Ask

the Librarian, Full Text Articles, Help Desk, Lecture Notes, Electronic Announcements, E-Books, Digital Suggestion Box, Project Reports, Frequently Asked Questions, Dissertations, Face Book, other Social Media these facilities can create a positive confidence towards the users.

New Books Display and Specialized Collections:

The Libraries must organize book exhibitions and special book collection on important dates and important occasion or celebrates the eminent personalities anniversary.i.e. National Science Day, Librarian's Day. This helps and provides an opportunity for users to know the various types of information resources available on a particular aspect in the library.

Developing Internet Based Services:

The library can use Internet based services like Social Networking, Blogging, Use of RSS Feed, Audio and Video streaming, Wikipedia and interacting delivery information services, it can save the time of users and get them timely information for further development on a particular topic.

Library Information Brochures:

Library brochures and pamphlets are one of the important sources for creating awareness about the facilities, services and the collections of the library. This brochures include information about the facilities of Xerox, Latest additions and publications to the library. Library rules – regulations, online information list.

Reservation and Renewal of Documents via E-Mails & SMS:

Many users for physically visited the library but according to 4th Law of Library Science. The users and library staffs time must be saved, so, using internet

reservation and renewal of books are possible now a days.

Social Networking:

These services are an online service that focuses on building and reflecting of social networks and social relations among the people. Social sites like facebook, Myspace can be used for this. Librarians can provide news or information for users, provide links to recommended internet resources, Book reviews, Information about new books, Research Tips.

Virtual Library:

It's a place from where access of all types of knowledge is on the desktop. It creates its own tools. The main goal is to provide virtual experience to the users due to the explosion of knowledge. It creates constant touch between learning resource center and the users.

Library 2.0:

The term Library 2.0 refers to a number of social and technological changes, which impact upon libraries, it's staff and their clientele and how they could interact. Library 2.0 is a concept that personified new generation of academic library services to meet the present day users need and expectations.

RFID Technology:

Radio frequency identification is used for technologies utilizing radio waves for identifying individual items automatically. It's one of today's exciting and fastest growing technologies for increasing efficiencies, improving profitability.¹²

Display of Various Library Charts:

The purpose of this practice is to advertise the library in a proper way. Charts are arranged and displayed in the library. E.g. Library advisory committee, Library staff and Library at a glance, Library vision, Library Mission & Objective of library, Rules of library,

Sections of library, Bay guides for every book racks.

Scholar Reader's Club:

The effectiveness of a Library and Information systems depend on the extent to which the system correspond with the users and how much the potential users are willing and able to make use of it.

Digital Library:

A Digital Library is a collection of documents in organized electronic form, available on the internet or on CD-ROM disks. Depending on the specific library, a user may be able to access e-resources, magazine articles, e-books.

ILL and MOU:

Library should has 'Memorandum of Understanding' with other organizations to share reading materials and E- resources. Library become member of DELNET, it provides inter library loan (ILL) facility to users.

Library Portal, Leaflets, Posters, Newsletters, Library Month, E-Commerce, Electronic Mail/Shots, News group, E-Reference Service, Publicity of Library Facilities are some nice practices.

Print Resources Facility:

1. Book Bank Facility – such facility can be made available for different level for Meritorious Students, For Low Income Group Students, For Group Book Bank
2. Special Collection for Competitive Exam Books- Some students are continuously appears for competitive exams, so, separate section for exam books, so, it's a necessity to make provision.

Best Practices in Management and Administration:

The best practices are a continuous and need based followed by any library. The expressed and unexpressed need or

problem are is identified. This helps in creating new ideas and changing them into applicable solutions. The failure or lacuna in the practice should be rectified with sportsman spirit. The success pay off in long runs and thus, help is creating openness of the library to change.

The core objective of the library is to support the academic program offered and library evolves its collection and services reflect into the curriculum requirement of its user. The library designed a system to deliver its products and services to attract more and more users. The library aim at bringing all its target users to the library for optimum usage.

Best Practices:

1. Needs of Different academic committees.
2. Employment information services by making separate section of newspaper.
3. Consistent documentation of individuals participation in learning and recognition of continuing learning in hiring and promotion decisions.
4. Notification Services by mounted Flex boards, directing Arrows, Informative Charts and library section map.
5. Displaying Newspaper clippings and maintaining soft copy.
6. Performance Appraisal of library staff.
7. Description of visit to National and International Library membership
8. Log in details of E- Resources, Search Strategy, Method of remote access of E-Library.
9. Library Advisory Committee and Students library committee should be active.
10. Administration and Maintenance of service area and generator facility is provided.
11. Invite the dignitaries for visiting the college libraries.
12. Professionally qualified library staff with masters degree in Library Science.
13. Reprography, Scanning and Printing facility.
14. Space innovation by custom made racks, area below staircase, electricity board due to

- dynamic changes.
15. Write articles in local dailies on the occasion of Dr. S.R. Rangnathan or any other eminent persons.
16. User friendly library staff.
17. First Aid Box with Periodic refilling.
18. Keep Fire Extinguisher **13.**

D.D.Shinde Sarkar Collge Library Best Practices:

Above all mentioned activities and best practices are done by our D.D.Shinde Sarkar College library, Kolhapur but with this our department maintain a '**Mobile Library**', This is the practice of Inculcating Reading Habbits, Many students are not interested to come in the library and many students are not get time to visit the library so, the library department initiates this practice and the library attendants with librarian going to the particular class with trolley- vehicle including 56-60 books (Marathi, Hindi, English),so the students see the books and users may inspire to read or arise interest. Another best practice is organize 'Vachan Katta' activity, in this the students take a review of book which they read earlier and they want to share with others. Students try to share the books, good quotations and most likely characters in the books, so, others are take keen interest to read the book.

Conclusion:

Library is the heart and brain of any institute. The best practices will help for improving quality of library services. This will create best image of the library profession in the society. The best practices adopted should bridge the gap between library and user for maximum utilization of the resources.

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